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Identification of the quasi-static behavior of a woven composite sensitive to the environmental conditions using numerical homogenization

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Automotive industry

Ecology

Composite materials

Some matrix and/or fibres are affected both by environmental conditions and strain rates

Issues in case of design

- Experimental characterization of the material
→ Long, expensive and cumbersome
- Desorption/ageing processes: ≈ 2.5 months
- Experiment : ≈ 2.5 months
→ 3 orientations, 5 specimens/test, 5 strain rates, 3 T° , 3 RH

Vacuum drying-chamber

Climate chamber

Suggested solution

- Numerical approach : double scale homogenization

Principle of the double scale homogenization

Matrix → data from experiment
Fibres → data from literature

- Fibres** → elastic fragile constitutive law
- Matrix** → development of a specific constitutive law (VMAT – ABAQUS) (isotropic elastic-plastic damageable)
- Yarn** → development of a specific constitutive law (VMAT – ABAQUS) (anisotropic elastic-plastic damageable)

Warp or weft direction

Shear direction

Conclusion

- *At ambient temperature and for both RH, satisfactory results*
- *Even if strong assumptions have been considered*
- *Numerical methodology allows to save time and to quickly obtain “main” characteristics useful in design*
- *Every steps (parameters identification, running and post-processing) can be quite automated*

Outlooks

- *Apply the methodology to all available experimental pair (temperature/RH)*
- *Introduce an inhomogeneity of RH inside the composite RVE*
- *Add cohesive elements or contact between fibres/yarn and matrix*
- *Use the numerical tool for others types of material*

Thank you for your attention, see you later for any question or discussion